

The Wonder of the Nolambas Architecture in Dharmapuri District

(Mallik Arjuneswarar Temple)

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Introduction

Dharmapuri District located on the North Western side of Tamil Nadu, It is often called the ‘City of Temples and Churches’; thus, making it a pilgrimage tourism hub with visitors from far and wide. These places of worship aren’t just about divinity, but beautiful architecture and natural splendour, making them ideal locations to meditate, pray and spend time. Some of the famous religious attractions like Shri Teerthagirishwara Temple, the Kottai Kovil Temple, the Chenraya Perumal Temple and the Mount Carmel Church. Dharmapuri offers many ideal locations if you are looking for a quiet place to relax and unwind.

Kottai Kovil is located on the northern side of the famous religious district of Dharmapuri in the southern state of Tamil Nadu. The deity in this temple is considered to be very powerful, and one who seeks the blessings always gets his or her wish fulfilled by the deity. The deity here in this temple is Lord Shiva.

There is a popular belief that this place was a part of the Hindu mythology Ramayana. People from across the state and also from the other states come to view the powerful deity. Moreover, some pictures and sculptures that are carved in the temple premises give an exotic view to the entire place. One of them a in features of Kottai Kovil temple is the hanging pillar.

Location

This temple is dedicated to God Mallikarjuneswarar and Goddess Kamatchi Ambal. It has been located at Madhikonpalayam near 1 km from Dharmapuri Bus stand.

Nolambasindharmapuri

The earliest known chieftain who ruled Tagadur present Dharmapuri during the Sangam era is Adigaman Naduman Anji, whose patronage sustained the famous poetess Avvaiyar. The 8th century when the northern parts of Tagadur were probably under the Pallavas regime. Subsequently, we hear of the Ganga Pallavas having sway over the Western parts of the Salem District. The Western Gangas are also mentioned as having ruled Baramahal during the end of the 8th century.

The history of Nolambalu is determined by geographical location. Their territory known as Nolambavadi included the modern districts of Tumkur, Chitradurga and Anantapur. They were therefore forced to play the role of buffer states between their neighbors the Banas and Vaidambas, as well as the great powers of the Deccan and South India.

Mahendra, his son by the Ganga princess, was the greatest of the Nolambas. He attacked his neighbours, the Vaidambas and the Batas, and claimed to have destroyed the latter. Certainly his kingdom included parts of Kolar and Bangalore districts and Dharmapuri in Salem district where his inscriptions are located.

Nolambas Art And Architecture

The role played by the Nolambas in South Indian political history may not be unique. Their art, though little known, is of great importance, and not only for its intrinsic beauty. The Rashtrakutas continued the wonderful tradition of early Chalukya art, but unfortunately only a few of their monuments survive. Not until the later Chalukyas are we again on firm ground. It is precisely this vacant period of the 9th-10th century – which was occupied by Nolamba art. And the Nolambas, whatever their political allegiance, were heirs to the Deccan tradition, which they developed and transmitted as far south as the Kolar district.

The Mallikarjuna temple door to the south of the main temple is well designed and predates the Rashtrakuta doors at Pattadakal, a Jain temple. The alternation of elaborately cut and plain beveled surfaces gives a striking effect. Famous features include two dwarves mounted on elephants and doors and windows. These dwarves carried Kuvera, the treasurer of two bees, a lotus flower and a conch, a motif of the Chalukyas, which was later adopted by the Cholas. The central figure of Gajalakshmi on the Mallikarjuna Gate also has two dwarves.

There are many sculptures about the site in small modern cells within the main temple complex. The southern type Surya is best barefoot and holding his lotus flowers (missing) very low. There is no more attractive image of this diety in Indian art.

Kottaikoil (or) Maligarjuneswarar Temple

The Kottai Kovil is also called as Fort temple, as it resembles a Fort and does not have a Raja Gopuram (main Temple Tower)!

There is a popular belief that the Kottai Kovil existed even during the period of Treta Yuga, when Lord Vishnu took the avatar of Lord Rama! It is believed that Lord Vishnu in his various avatars as Yoga Narasimha, Hayagriva, Lord Rama and Lord Krishna, had worshipped Lord Mallikarjuneswara in Kottai Kovil! Several Tamil poets like Avvaiyar, Parinar, Kabilar, Sambandar and Sundarar had sung the glory of Lord Mallikarjuneswara in Dharmapuri!

Hanging Pillars

The Kottai Kovil was built between the 8th - 9th Century A.D. The specialty of this temple is its amazing architecture, rare sculptures and paintings. Lord Vinayaka is worshipped here as Selva Ganapati. One of the main features of the Kottai Kovil temple is the presence of two hanging pillars weighing 2.5 tons! These amazing pillars are located in the Ardha Mandapam, just next to the 'Garbha Griha' (Sanctum Sanctorum) of this temple. The devotees can clearly see a 2 cm space between the base and the pillar!

At the Mallikarjuneswarar temple in Dharmapuri fort stands — or should we say hangs — a sculptural wonder: A pillar suspended for more than 1,200 years. The structure at the 'Kottai Koil' or fort temple can be traced to the eighth century 'Nulambar' period of the Pallava dynasty. "The pillar hangs 2cm above the ground. The space is clearly visible. You can slide a piece of cloth or paper under the pillar," says C.Chandrashekar, archaeologist and professor in the history department at Dharmapuri Govt Arts College.

Kottai Kovil, located on the northern side of Dharmapuri, is temple dedicated to Lord Shiva. As per the locale belief, a secret passage in this temple connects it to Adhiyamankottai. The place has some great religious significance as thousands of devotees come here to worship

the deity. The Mallikarjuneswara temple in Dharmapuri district stands out for its architecture. Presiding Deity is called as Mallikarjuneswar and Mother is called as Kamakshi amman.

The Temple is considered as Thevara Vaippu Sthalam as Devaram hymns sung by Sundarar. The Temple is believed to be 1000 years old. There is a popular belief that this place was a part of the mythology Ramayana. One of the main features of Kottai Kovil temple is the Hanging pillar

Puranic significance

Lord Shiva is a swayambumurthy in the temple. There are two hanging pillars speaking volumes of the sculptural skill of Tamilnadu. Emphasizing the greatness of Motherhood, the shrine of mother is at a higher level than of Lord. It has been renovated and is maintained by the government and people of Dharmapuri. Saint Puri Siddha appealed to Kulothunga Chola to renovate the shrine which was then known as Thirualiswaram, and accordingly, the king renovated the temple which came to be called 'Chanayiram Muzhamayiram'. The inscriptions speak of the renovations made from time to time by several kings including Tipu Sultan.

Sundaramurthy Nayanar, in one of his hymns, gives a passing reference to the temple. According to the puranic story there was a secret passage that connects this temple to Adhiyamankottai. There are carvings of Ramayana the base of the temple in counter clock direction. There is a popular belief that this place was a part of the Hindu mythology Ramayana. People from across the state and also from the other states come to view the powerful deity. One of the main features of Kottai Kovil temple is the Hanging pillar. To win the Kurukshetra war, Arjuna performed penance on Lord Shiva seeking the Pasupatha weapon boon. When Lord appeared before him to judge the purity of the penance, both entered into a war of words in connection with the killing of a pig and this burst into wrestling between them. Arjuna struck Lord with his bow. Lord appeared before Arjuna in real form. Arjuna fell at his feet and sought pardon with tears in eyes. Lord Shiva was happy to bless Arjuna with the Pasupatha weapon. From Sage Bharadwaja, Arjuna learnt that he had committed a sin by striking Lord.

He performed Shiva Puja here with jasmine flowers – Mallikai in Tamil. Hence Lord is praised as Mallika Arjuna –Mallikarjuna. Chera King, Cheraman Peruman knowing the glory of

the place, worshipped Lord Shiva in this temple. The shrine is considered one among the 1,008 ancient Siva temples. It was here that Indrajit, son of Ravana, performed a sacrifice to get boons from Goddess Nikumbalai. This is also the only temple where Prathyankira and Sulini, consorts of Sarabha, are worshipped.

Beliefs

Prayer in the temple is an effective treatment of diseases of any kind, say devotees. Above all, they are blessed with mental peace. People also pray for wedding, child, and family welfare boons and for relief from burden of debts

Special features

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Sculptures & Shrines of Mallikarjuneswarar Temple

Apart from the Hanging pillar the rest of the pillars, have the same lion sculpture at joints as this one has, but all the rest are chopped off their head. The ceiling has the whole **Navagraha** sculpted in it in full essence, in full rhythm. Separately on the side is these parate shrine for Ambal who is here as Kamakshi Amman who face seas there. She is a gain a wedding speciality Goddess and so she's also called **Kalyana Kamakshi Amman**. The number of steps to reach her shrine is 18. This denotes the 18 good habits to be cultivated in the self together complete blessings. Her shrines is in a shape of an 18 pointed star. This denoted that the Ambal here has all the 18 Viththunai Sakthigal (mystical powers).

In the circum-ambulation passage, in the space that's between the elephants has the whole description of **Ramayana**. Ramayana is the story of Sri Ram who is an incarnation of Lord Vishnu. Ramayana is one of the 2 epics of India with the other one being

Mahabaratha. Ramanayana is sculpted scene by scene in the 1 foot base of the shrine. Their sculpting marvel is evident here as well. Infact the pregnant ladies in the scene are shown so realistically that I couldn't resist my temptation to feel their bulged bellies. The story begins right behind Ambal and goes left to right that's in Apradakshinam or Opposite pradakshina or circum-ambulation.

This is sculpted so as when someone goes following the story they circumambulate Kamakshi in wrong direction. We circum-ambulate seeking the blessings. But later when we lose interest in worldly things and seek inner peace and tend to move towards Godliness, we change the direction of circum-ambulation.

There is another separate shrine for **Arumugar** or Lord Muruga aka Lord Karthikeya. He sits on his mount Peacock and there is a snake crawling beneath his foot. This is to denote that the snake carries the foot of Lord Arumugar from touching the ground. The temple priest Selva Muthu Kumaraswami was such a nice person who took time to explain each and every thing even after Nadai Mooduthal (Closure of temple for noon).

Festivals

Aadipooram bangle festival and Friday Sandal Alankara and Poopandhal in July-August; 2 day Thai month Chandi Homa in January-February; Margazhi special pujas and Vaikunda Ekadasi festivals in December and January; Vaikasi Car Festival in May-June; Navarathri in September- October are the main festivals celebrated in the temple. Also monthly pradosha days, Tamil and English New Year days are also observed drawing huge devotee crowd.

Referances:

1. nrh.rhe;jy;q;fk "வரலலாற்றறில்தக^ர"> தக^ரமலாவட்டவரலலாற்றும்பபேரவவ>தருமபுலாறி>1990.
2. சுப்பேறிமணறியன.தறி>"தருமபுலாறிநடுகல்அகழ்வவப்பேகம்வகபயடு">தமறிழ்நலாடுஅரசுததலால்லியல்துவற>த செனவன.2010
3. தமறிழ்நலாட்டுவரலலாற்றுக்குழுவறினர>"ததலால்பேழங்கலாலம்">தமறிழ்நலாட்டுவரலலாற்றுக்குழுவறினர>த செனவன>1975.

4. மலாரகசெறியகலாந்தறி.நலா> “தமறிழகவரலலாற்றறில் அதறியர மரபு”> அமுதன பேதறிப்பேகம்>தசெனவன>2009.
5. Excavation of Archaeological sites in Tamil Nadu “Modur2004-2005”, Department of Archaeology, Government of Tamil Nadu, Chennai. 2005.
6. Rajan, K, “Archaeological Gazetteer of Tamil Nadu”, Manoo Pathippakam, Thanjavur, 1997.
7. Subramanian. T, “Tamilakath Tholiayl Varalarul, Thagadur Region” New Century Book House, Chennai, 2009.
8. LeFanu,H.A.A Manual of the Salem District in the Madras Presidency, Vols. I &II. Madras: 1883.
9. Pulney Andy Senji. Tamil Nadu District Gazetteers, Dharmapuri. Government of Tamil Nadu, 1995.
10. Richards, F.J. Madras District Gazetteers, Salem, Volume I& Part I& II, Vol.2. Madras: Government Press, 1918.
11. Idappadi Amudhan. Kongunattil Munro, Idappadi: Anuradha Phippakam, 2011.
12. Krishnamoorthy,S. Dharumapuri Mavatta Tholliyal Kaiyedu. Chennai: Special commissioner of Archaeology, 2005.
13. Seminar on social and cultural History of Dharmapuri District.” Institute of Kongu Nadu Studies, Salem, 24 – 25 April 1983.
14. Tamil Murasu, Dharmapuri special Edition (Evening),29.10.2012
15. Interview: Balasubramani Gurukkal. Kottaikiol, Dharmapuri Dated:23.10.22